

FINE-TUNING OKRA TRAITS: "EXPLORING SELECTION INDICES IN AGRICULTURAL RESEARCH"

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Abstract

This experiment was comprising of fifty different genotypes of okra from wide- ranging origin. For constructing the selection indices, the characters which had highly significant and positive correlation with okra yield per plant were considered. In this context, the fruit yield per plant (X_1) along with five components characters viz., plant height (X_2), internode length (X_3), fruit weight (X_4), number of nodes per plant (X_5) and total chlorophyll content (X_6) were identified and considered. The function's selection efficiency was found to improve by increasing the number of characters in the selection index. The index that included all five characteristics recorded the greatest genetic gain and selection efficiency. viz. fruit yield per plant, plant height, internode length, fruit weight, number of nodes per plant ($X_1+X_2 + X_3+X_4+X_5$) were resulted more suitable for selecting the parents for hybridization.

Keywords: Okra, expected genetic advance, selection Indices

Introduction

Okra [*Abelmoschus esculentus* (L.) Moench], a member of the malvaceae family with chromosomal number $2n=130$, has risen to prominence among vegetables. It is a desirable fruit vegetable that is widely produced in tropical, subtropical, and warm regions of the world such as India, Africa, Turkey, and its neighboring nations. Fresh okra pods are the most important vegetable source of viscous fiber, an important dietary component to lower cholesterol. Fresh okra pods that are seven days old contain the maximum nutritious content. Okra is abundant in fiber, which "assists in blood sugar stabilization by moderating the pace at which sugar is absorbed from the intestine." The frequent usage of okra might help avoid kidney disease. In India, the okra crop has been grown in 0.532 million hectares area having production of 6.513 million tonnes (Anon., 2021a). The okra growing states are Andhra Pradesh, Gujarat, Uttar Pradesh, Maharashtra, Haryana, Punjab, Tamil Nadu and Karnataka. In Gujarat, main okra growing districts are Surat, Tapi, Navsari, Vadodara, Bharuch, Banaskantha, Anand, Kheda and Mahesana. In Gujarat, it is grown on area about 0.85 million hectares with production of 1.018 million tonnes (Anon., 2021b).

Discriminant function analysis revealed that when the selection was based on component character, the selection efficiency was greater in general than straight selection, and this increased as more characters were added to the index. When five characters were evaluated combined, the maximum efficiency was observed.

Materials and Methods

Fifty genotypes of okra collected from different origin evaluated in Randomized Complete Block Design with three replications at the Main Vegetable Research Station, Anand Agricultural University, Anand. It was decided to use a 60 cm row to row and 30 cm plant to plant spacing. Six characteristics were recorded on five randomly chosen plants of each genotype and replication, adhering to the advised packages of practices. Traits namely, X_1 =fruit yield per plant, X_2 =plant height, X_3 =internode length, X_4 =fruit weight, X_5 =number of nodes per plant and X_6 =total chlorophyll content.

Methods

The selection indices were created using Dabholkar's (1999) discriminant function analysis. Only those characters with a significant correlation and a direct effect on fruit yield were chosen for this study.

Result and discussions

For constructing the selection indices, the characters which had highly significant and positive correlation with seed okra yield per plant were considered. In this context, the fruit yield per plant (X_1) along with five components characters viz., plant height (X_2), internode length (X_3), fruit weight (X_4), number of nodes per plant (X_5) and total chlorophyll content (X_6) were identified and considered. Total 63 selection indices (6 for single characters, 15 for combination of two characters, 20 for combination of three

characters, 15 for combination of four characters, 6 for combination of five characters and 1 for all six characters) were constructed in all possible combination of the five yield contributing characters and fruit yield per plant. The expected genetic advance obtained from selection index of fruit yield per plant with equal weight was considered as base to work out per cent relative efficiency (PRE) for different indices with assuming the efficiency of selection for fruit yield per plant as 100%. The selection indices with their expected genetic advance and per cent relative efficiency are presented in Table 1.

The relative efficiency (%)

Among the single character index, per cent relative efficiency (PRE) ranged from 1.01 to 100.00. The maximum efficiency of 100.00% was exhibited by fruit yield per plant followed by plant height (37.72%).

Among the combination involving two component characters, PRE ranged between 4.94 (I_{34}) [internode length and fruit weight] to 125.94 (I_{12}) [fruit yield per plant and plant height]. Fruit yield per plant and plant height (I_{12}) exhibited maximum relative efficiency of 125.94% followed by fruit yield per plant and fruit weight (I_{14}); fruit yield per plant and internode length (I_{13}); fruit yield per plant and number of nodes per plant (I_{15}) and fruit yield per plant and total chlorophyll content (I_{16}) having relative efficiency of 103.94%, 102.83%, 101.33% and 99.10% respectively.

The selection index based on three-character combination indicated that a discriminant function with fruit yield per plant, plant height and fruit weight (I_{134}) possessed maximum relative efficiency of 129.36%. Similarly, fruit yield per plant, plant height and internode length (I_{123}); fruit yield per plant, plant height and number of nodes per plant (I_{125}); fruit yield per plant, plant height and total chlorophyll content (I_{126}); fruit yield per plant, internode length and fruit weight (I_{134}) and fruit yield per plant, internode length, number of nodes per plant (I_{135}) also exhibited high relative efficiency of 129.30%, 127.52%, 125.34%, 106.77% and 104.51% respectively.

Among the combination involving four component characters, PRE ranged from 8.42 (I_{3456}) [internode length, fruit weight, number of nodes per plant and total chlorophyll content] to 132.72 (I_{1234}) [fruit yield per plant, plant height, internode length and fruit weight]. Fruit yield per plant, plant height, internode length and fruit weight (I_{1234}) exerted maximum relative efficiency of 132.72 followed by fruit yield per plant, plant height, internode length and number of nodes per plant (I_{1235}); fruit yield per plant, plant height, fruit weight and number of nodes per plant (I_{1245}); fruit yield per plant, plant height, fruit weight and total chlorophyll content (I_{1246}) and fruit yield per plant, plant height, internode length and total chlorophyll content (I_{1236}) exhibited high relative efficiency of 131.69%, 130.94%, 128.80% and 128.43% respectively.

The selection index based on five-character combination indicated that a discriminant function with fruit yield per plant, plant height,

internode length, fruit weight and number of nodes per plant (I_{12345}) possessed maximum relative efficiency of 135.04%. Similarly, fruit yield per plant, plant height, internode length, fruit weight and total chlorophyll content (I_{12346}); fruit yield per plant, plant height, internode length, number of nodes per plant and total chlorophyll content (I_{12356}); fruit yield per plant, plant height, fruit weight, number of nodes per plant and total chlorophyll content (I_{12456}) and fruit yield per plant, internode length, fruit weight and total chlorophyll content (I_{13456}) also exhibited high relative efficiency of 131.88%, 131.06%, 130.45% and 107.70% respectively.

The selection index based on six-character combination indicated that a discriminant function with fruit yield per plant, plant height, internode length, fruit weight, number of nodes per plant and total chlorophyll content (I_{123456}) possessed maximum relative efficiency of 134.00%.

Table 1. Selection indices, expected genetic advance and per cent relative efficiency (PRE) for single character and all possible combination of the five yield contributing characters and fruit yield per plant.

Among all the 63 selection indices, the index based on six characters *viz.*, fruit yield per plant, plant height, internode length, fruit weight and number of nodes per plant (I_{12345}) possessed the highest genetic advance and relative efficiency (52.49 g and 135.04%) as compared to straight selection for fruit yield per plant. Other important selection index identified was with the inclusion of five characters *viz.*, fruit yield per plant, plant height, internode length, fruit weight, number of nodes per plant and total chlorophyll content (I_{123456}) that possessed higher genetic advance (52.25 g) and relative efficiency (134.00 %). Total sixty selection indices contracted involving fruit yield and five yield contributing characters in okra by Ramgiry *et al.* (2023); in a similar study, sixty -eight advanced breeding lines contracted by fruit yield and five yield contributing characters in okra by Monpara and Chhatrolla (2010).

Sr. No.	Equation	Genetic advance	PRE
I₁	I=0.6299X₁	38.87	100.00
I ₂	I=0.7785X ₂	14.66	37.72
I ₃	I=0.8611X ₃	1.73	4.46
I ₄	I=0.2611X ₄	0.47	1.20
I ₅	I=0.865X ₅	3.39	8.73
I ₆	I=0.9834X ₆	2.53	6.51
I₁₂	I=0.6106X₁+1.1275X₂	49.00	125.94
I ₁₃	I=0.6157X ₁ +3.755X ₃	40.00	102.83
I ₁₄	I=0.5876X ₁ +5.1023X ₄	40.40	103.94
I ₁₅	I=0.6279X ₁ +1.0491X ₅	39.40	101.33
I ₁₆	I=0.6224X ₁ +0.3151X ₆	38.50	99.10
I ₂₃	I=0.6769X ₂ +2.6698X ₃	16.40	42.27
I ₂₄	I=0.7834X ₂ +0.5216X ₄	14.90	38.28
I ₂₅	I=0.7745X ₂ +0.7793X ₅	15.70	40.45
I ₂₆	I=0.7788X ₂ +1.0438X ₆	15.00	38.53
I ₃₄	I=0.9087X ₃ +0.2947X ₄	1.92	4.94
I ₃₅	I=0.8015X ₃ +0.8394X ₅	2.83	7.27
I ₃₆	I=0.8482X ₃ +0.9558X ₆	2.64	6.80
I ₄₅	I=0.2591X ₄ +0.8804X ₅	3.51	9.03
I ₄₆	I=0.2671X ₄ +0.9707X ₆	2.53	6.50
I ₅₆	I=0.856X ₅ +1.0578X ₆	4.93	12.69
I ₁₂₃	I=0.6139X ₁ +0.9265X ₂ +4.2305X ₃	50.26	129.30
I₁₂₄	I=0.5662X₁+1.1338X₂+5.2417X₄	50.28	129.36
I ₁₂₅	I=0.611X ₁ +1.1396X ₂ +0.4981X ₅	49.57	127.52
I ₁₂₆	I=0.601X ₁ +1.1429X ₂ +0.39X ₆	48.72	125.34
I ₁₃₄	I=0.5718X ₁ +3.8613X ₃ +5.2009X ₄	41.50	106.77
I ₁₃₅	I=0.598X ₁ +5.1676X ₃ +2.2208X ₅	40.62	104.51
I ₁₃₆	I=0.6119X ₁ +3.5084X ₃ +0.1114X ₆	39.52	101.67
I ₁₄₅	I=0.5858X ₁ +5.1073X ₄ +1.0108X ₅	40.91	105.24
I ₁₄₆	I=0.5793X ₁ +5.149X ₄ +0.36X ₆	40.07	103.10
I ₁₅₆	I=0.617X ₁ +1.3753X ₅ +0.5032X ₆	39.15	100.72
I ₂₃₄	I=0.6798X ₂ +2.6916X ₃ +0.591X ₄	16.65	42.84
I ₂₃₅	I=0.2743X ₂ +6.9907X ₃ +3.0566X ₅	17.71	45.57
I ₂₃₆	I=0.6642X ₂ +2.8602X ₃ +1.4061X ₆	16.67	42.88
I ₂₄₅	I=0.7792X ₂ +0.5365X ₄ +0.7813X ₅	15.94	41.02
I ₂₄₆	I=0.7836X ₂ +0.5304X ₄ +1.0361X ₆	15.18	39.06
I ₂₅₆	I=0.7764X ₂ +0.7448X ₅ +1.1712X ₆	16.22	41.73
I ₃₄₅	I=0.8858X ₃ +0.2942X ₄ +0.8761X ₅	3.04	7.83
I ₃₄₆	I=0.8946X ₃ +0.3005X ₄ +0.9523X ₆	2.73	7.02
I ₃₅₆	I=0.81X ₃ +0.8379X ₅ +1.0318X ₆	4.29	11.03
I ₄₅₆	I=0.2687X ₄ +0.8757X ₅ +1.0359X ₆	4.99	12.84
I₁₂₃₄	I=0.5688X₁+0.9259X₂+4.3424X₃+5.3214X₄	51.58	132.72
I ₁₂₃₅	I=0.6157X ₁ +0.315X ₂ +10.8216X ₃ +4.2131X ₅	51.19	131.69
I ₁₂₃₆	I=0.608X ₁ +0.9603X ₂ +3.8362X ₃ +0.1863X ₆	49.92	128.43

I ₁₂₄₅	$I=0.5663X_1+1.1488X_2+5.2752X_4+0.4474X_5$	50.89	130.94
I ₁₂₄₆	$I=0.5558X_1+1.1497X_2+5.2929X_4+0.4401X_6$	50.06	128.80
I ₁₂₅₆	$I=0.602X_1+1.1376X_2+0.7775X_5+0.2745X_6$	49.37	127.02
I ₁₃₄₅	$I=0.5544X_1+5.259X_3+5.1883X_4+2.207X_5$	42.13	108.40
I ₁₃₄₆	$I=0.5676X_1+3.6071X_3+5.2287X_4+0.0822X_6$	41.07	105.66
I ₁₃₅₆	$I=0.5888X_1+5.0766X_3+2.4945X_5+0.3756X_6$	40.33	103.77
I ₁₄₅₆	$I=0.5744X_1+5.1431X_4+1.3428X_5+0.5318X_6$	40.68	104.67
I ₂₃₄₅	$I=0.2709X_2+7.0835X_3+0.5734X_4+3.0931X_5$	17.95	46.17
I ₂₃₄₆	$I=0.6668X_2+2.8824X_3+0.6229X_4+1.4048X_6$	16.88	43.42
I ₂₃₅₆	$I=0.2717X_2+7.0587X_3+3.0199X_5+1.3X_6$	18.10	46.56
I ₂₄₅₆	$I=0.7808X_2+0.5536X_4+0.7486X_5+1.1622X_6$	16.43	42.26
I ₃₄₅₆	$I=0.8917X_3+0.302X_4+0.8768X_5+1.0164X_6$	4.41	11.33
I₁₂₃₄₅	$I=0.5712X_1+0.3205X_2+10.8653X_3+5.2634X_4+4.1789X_5$	52.49	135.04
I ₁₂₃₄₆	$I=0.5624X_1+0.9609X_2+3.9335X_3+5.3483X_4+0.1552X_6$	51.26	131.88
I ₁₂₃₅₆	$I=0.6083X_1+0.331X_2+10.6129X_3+4.3625X_5-0.0368X_6$	50.94	131.06
I ₁₂₄₅₆	$I=0.5568X_1+1.1468X_2+5.3067X_4+0.7327X_5-0.3035X_6$	50.71	130.45
I ₁₃₄₅₆	$I=0.5447X_1+5.1666X_3+5.2205X_4+2.4856X_5-0.4017X_6$	41.86	107.70
I ₂₃₄₅₆	$I=0.5568X_1+1.1468X_2+5.3067X_4+0.7327X_5-0.3035X_6$	18.32	47.14
I₁₂₃₄₅₆	$I=0.5632X_1+0.337X_2+10.6504X_3+5.2917X_4+4.3317X_5-0.0647X_6$	52.25	134.00

Where, I₁, I₂, I₃... are selection indices and X₁=fruit yield per plant, X₂=plant height, X₃=internode length, X₄=fruit weight, X₅=number of nodes per plant and X₆=total chlorophyll content, PRE=per cent relative efficiency

Table 2. Scores and ranking of fifty genotypes of okra based on various trait combinations of the five yield contributing characters and fruit yield per plant

Genotypes	Score (4)	Rank (4)	Score (5)	Rank (5)	Score (6)	Rank (6)
AOL 18-06	157.393	37	196.779	39	197.208	39
AOL 18-12	193.781	8	234.992	8	235.168	9
AOL 19-10	157.841	35	197.738	38	197.947	37
AOL 18-08	160.025	32	198.785	35	198.888	36
AOL 19-06	183.376	18	222.35	19	222.238	19
AOL 18-10	165.926	28	205.741	30	205.465	30
AOL 19-05	128.409	49	166.446	49	166.913	49
AOL 19-12	142.342	45	185.933	44	186.926	44
AOL 19-09	185.071	16	225.469	15	225.713	15
AOL 19-03	186.522	14	230.794	11	231.826	11
AOL 20-10	207.503	3	247.621	4	247.738	4
AOL 19-07	140.403	46	179.109	46	179.375	46
AOL 18-11	181.794	20	219.597	22	219.403	22
AOL 19-08	192.442	9	233.482	10	233.522	10
AOL 20-03	157.407	36	212.667	25	214.467	24
AOL 20-04	207.392	4	249.447	3	249.855	3
AOL 20-06	154.592	39	198.607	36	199.184	35
AOL 16-23	196.316	6	236.933	7	237.218	7
RED ONE LONG	157.192	38	199.636	34	200.232	34
VRO 5	215.699	2	259.827	2	260.158	2
VRO 6	190.084	11	230.572	12	230.791	12
KRISHI KRANTI	189.067	12	229.63	13	229.923	13
PUNJAB SUHAVANI	176.82	23	215.551	23	215.473	23
VARSHA UPHAR	162.973	31	203.076	31	203.398	31
GO 2	222.034	1	262.621	1	262.152	1
GO 6	203	5	244.903	5	245.231	5
PRABHANI KRANTI	192.28	10	234.917	9	235.399	8
ARKA ANAMIKA	173.227	24	213.485	24	213.824	25
ARKA ABHAY	185.542	15	224.176	16	223.941	17
PHULE PRAJATIKA	184.03	17	221.775	20	221.232	21
JF 108-02	165.723	29	206.904	29	207.387	29
PHULE VIMUKTA	145.024	44	182.687	45	182.914	45
AOL 21-01	148.295	42	188.226	43	188.825	43
AOL 21-02	159.994	33	201.613	32	202.209	33
AOL 21-07	195.45	7	237.81	6	238.33	6
AOL 21-09	168.247	26	211.349	27	212.017	27

AOL 21-10	148.278	43	195.685	40	196.695	40
AOL 21-12	138.083	47	173.605	47	173.609	47
GP OK 8	121.619	50	162.578	50	163.463	50
GP OK 10	181.869	19	223.599	17	223.896	18
GP OK 21	129.716	48	169.896	48	170.361	48
GP OK 24	173.212	25	212.26	26	212.256	26
GP OK 26	152.773	41	191.943	42	192.262	42
GP OK 27	163.041	30	208.168	28	209.006	28
GP OK 34	180.55	21	223.571	18	224.087	16
GP OK 35	158.851	34	201.392	33	202.214	32
GAO 5	186.716	13	226.97	14	226.911	14
PUSA SAWANI	177.34	22	221.381	21	222.053	20
GAO 8: Anand Komal	154.059	40	193.217	41	193.397	41

Note: Values in parenthesis indicates the respective trait combination for scores and ranks

Conclusion:

Combination of fruit yield and its attributing characters (plant height, internode length, fruit weight, number of nodes per plant and total chlorophyll content) gave high genetic advance and percent relative efficiency therefore, these characters can be used to select elite genotypes.

Based on the highest scores promising genotypes were identified. (Table 2) GO 2 had the highest score in (fruit yield per plant, plant height, internode length, fruit weight, number of nodes per plant and total chlorophyll content) trait combination, followed by VRO 5, AOL 20-10, AOL 20-04 and GO 6. These genotypes were used for further breeding programme.

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